

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	CTU4H35A
Principle Investigator	Gerhard Groebner
Structure/Description	<p>1-palmitoyl-<i>d</i>₃₁-2-oleoyl-<i>d</i>₃₂-<i>sn</i>-glycerophosphocholine</p>
Code	OB_121
Producer	Oliver Bogojevic
Mass	36 mg
% Deuteration	OB_121: 92% across entire molecule
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{32} -*sn*-glycerophosphocholine (OB_121) in CD_3OD (400 MHz).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{32} -*sn*-glycerophosphocholine (OB_121) in CD_3OD (400 MHz) (expansion).

Figure 3. ESI-MS(pos) of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{32} -*sn*-glycerophosphocholine (OB_121): m/z calculated for $C_{42}H_{18}D_{64}NO_8P [M+H]^+$ as 824.97 (natural abundance); found: 821.9 (most abundant isotopologue).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution								
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit								
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:	Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	75,0	1,0000E+00	1,0000E+00	0,4	¹³ C # 2	75,0	1,0000E+00	0,5
2	76,6	1,1000E+00	6,4600E-01	0,2	¹³ C # 3	76,6	6,4600E-01	0,3
3	78,1	1,3000E+00	6,9960E-01	0,3		78,1	6,9960E-01	0,3
4	79,7	1,8000E+00	1,0987E+00	0,4		79,7	1,0987E+00	0,5
5	81,3	2,8000E+00	1,6515E+00	0,6	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks	81,3	1,6515E+00	0,8
6	82,8	3,6000E+00	2,2378E+00	0,9	2,1230E+02	82,8	2,2378E+00	1,1
7	84,4	5,1000E+00	3,2030E+00	1,3	Average % Deuteration of Molecule	84,4	3,2030E+00	1,5
8	85,9	8,4000E+00	5,7210E+00	2,3	92,0	85,9	5,7210E+00	2,7
9	87,5	1,2000E+01	7,6713E+00	3,2	Error = +/- 2 %	87,5	7,6713E+00	3,6
10	89,1	2,0100E+01	1,3804E+01	5,8		89,1	1,3804E+01	6,5
11	90,6	3,0300E+01	1,9963E+01	8,5		90,6	1,9963E+01	9,4
12	92,2	5,8400E+01	4,2614E+01	18,5		92,2	4,2614E+01	20,1
13	93,8	8,4000E+01	5,4426E+01	24,0		93,8	5,4426E+01	25,6
14	95,3	1,0000E+02	5,5966E+01	25,1		95,3	5,5966E+01	26,4
15	96,9	7,4600E+01	2,0716E+01	9,5		96,9	2,0716E+01	9,8
16	98,4	3,7700E+01	-6,2684E+00	-2,9		98,4	-6,2684E+00	-3,0
17	100,0	1,1800E+01	-1,2850E+01	-6,1		100,0	-1,2850E+01	-6,1
18			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
19			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
20			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
21			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
22			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
23			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
24			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
25			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
26			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
27			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
28			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
29			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
30			0,0000E+00	0,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0

Figure 4. Calculation of the level of deuteration for 1-palmitoyl-*d*₃₁-2-oleoyl-*d*₃₂-*sn*-glycerophosphocholine (OB_121), based on ESI-MS.